

Supplemental Table 1. Sequence of primers for real-time PCR

Gene	Accession Number	Primer sequences (5'-3')	Reverse
		Forward	
<i>Adiponectin</i>	NM_009605	TGTTCCCTCTTAATCCTGCCCA	CCAACCTGCACAAGTTCCTT
<i>Adipsin</i>	NM_013459	CATGCTCGGCCCTACATGG	CACAGAGTCGTCATCCGTCAC
<i>Car3</i>	NM_007606	TGACAGGTCTATGCTGAGGGG	CAGCGTATTTTACTCCGTCCAC
<i>Selenbp1</i>	NM_009150	ATGGCTACAAAATGCACAAAGTG	CCTGTGTTCCGGTAAATGCAG
<i>Cyp2f2</i>	NM_007817	GGACCCAAACCTCTCCAATC	CCGTGAACACCGACCCATAC
<i>Glut4</i>	NM_009204	CTGTGCTGGTTTCTCCAA	CTGCTCTAAAAGGGAAGGTGTC
<i>Acc</i>	NM_133360	GATGAACCATCTCCGTTGGC	GACCCAATTATGAATCGGGAGTG
<i>Fas</i>	NM_007988	GGAGGTGGTGATAGCCGGTAT	TGGGTAATCCATAGAGCCAG
<i>Scd1</i>	NM_009127	TTCTTGCGATACACTCTGGTGC	CGGGATTGAATGTTCTTGTCTG
<i>Cd36</i>	NM_001159558	ATGGGCTGTGATCGGAACTG	TTTGCCACGTCATCTGGGTTT
<i>Fabp4</i>	NM_024406	AAGGTGAAGAGCATCATAACCCT	TCACGCCTTTCATAACACATTCC
<i>Pparγ</i>	NM_001127330	GGAAGACCACTCGCATTCTT	GTAATCAGCAACCATTGGGTCA
<i>Col3a1</i>	NM_009930	CTGTAACATGGAACTGGGGAAA	CCATAGCTGAACTGAAAACCACC
<i>Col5a1</i>	NM_015734	CTTCGCCGCTACTCCTGTTT	CCCTGAGGGCAAATTGTGAAAA
<i>Col6a1</i>	NM_009933	CTGCTGCTACAAGCCTGCT	CCCCATAAGGTTTCAGCCTCA
<i>Cebpa</i>	NM_007678	CAAGAACAGCAACGAGTACCG	GTCCTGGTCAACTCCAGCAC
<i>Lipin1</i>	NM_015763	CATGCTTCGGAAAAGTCCTTCA	GGTTATTCTTTGGCGTCAACCT
<i>Gpam</i>	NM_008149	ACAGTTGGCACAATAGACGTTT	CCTTCCATTTTCAGTGTTGCAGA
<i>Fads3</i>	NM_021890	TGACCTACCAGGCGACAAGT	CAATCAACAGGGGTTTCAGGAA
<i>36b4</i>	NM_007475	GCAGACAACGTGGGCTCCAAGCAGAT	GGTCCTCCTTGGTGAACACGAAGCCC

Supplemental Table 2. Lists of DEGs that were changed in white adipose tissue (WAT) by *Nampt* knockout in young and/or old mice.

(A) DEGs (142 genes) that were changed by *Nampt* knockout only in young mice but not in old mice.

Gene symbol	Young (Log₂ FC)	Young (FDR)	Old (Log₂ FC)	Old (FDR)
<i>Ncam2</i>	-3.76	1.14E-05	-1.69	3.04E-01
<i>2810459M11Rik</i>	-2.99	2.63E-05	-2.28	7.03E-02
<i>1810046K07Rik</i>	-1.82	1.46E-02	1.33	1.47E-01
<i>Sctr</i>	-1.80	1.33E-04	-1.68	1.38E-01
<i>Itih4</i>	-1.60	8.76E-03	0.92	7.57E-01
<i>Lrg1</i>	-1.59	2.98E-08	-0.96	2.51E-01
<i>Itпка</i>	-1.59	2.26E-02	-0.78	7.44E-01
<i>Adra1a</i>	-1.45	2.56E-05	-1.39	5.64E-02
<i>Gpx3</i>	-1.38	3.50E-04	-0.79	4.84E-01
<i>Fgf14</i>	-1.38	1.17E-02	-0.53	9.26E-01
<i>Angpt1</i>	-1.33	5.42E-05	-0.99	1.81E-01
<i>Rgs7bp</i>	-1.31	1.48E-04	-1.58	7.92E-02
<i>Podn</i>	-1.28	6.75E-11	-0.92	2.12E-01
<i>Hoxb8</i>	-1.21	3.17E-02	-0.44	9.43E-01
<i>Irf4</i>	-1.17	2.49E-03	0.58	3.52E-01
<i>Sh2d4b</i>	-1.16	7.13E-03	-0.84	4.46E-01
<i>Endou</i>	-1.10	2.50E-02	-1.03	3.71E-01
<i>Plod2</i>	-1.10	1.67E-03	-0.27	1.00E+00
<i>Papss2</i>	-1.08	9.72E-07	-0.82	9.87E-02
<i>Fam214a</i>	-1.07	2.41E-05	-0.95	5.61E-02
<i>Slc16a7</i>	-1.06	4.79E-04	-1.01	5.35E-02
<i>D3Erttd751e</i>	-1.01	2.02E-03	-0.75	2.59E-01
<i>Net1</i>	-1.00	2.50E-04	-0.87	5.31E-02
<i>Pfkl</i>	1.01	1.67E-02	-0.60	4.97E-01
<i>Ppp1r15a</i>	1.01	1.04E-03	0.32	4.97E-01
<i>Afap1</i>	1.01	1.91E-02	-0.58	4.62E-01
<i>Cdr2</i>	1.02	3.53E-02	-1.08	6.71E-02
<i>Cdkn1a</i>	1.02	2.30E-03	-0.43	9.88E-01
<i>Spire1</i>	1.03	6.30E-04	-0.27	1.00E+00
<i>Slc16a1</i>	1.04	3.52E-03	-0.83	3.12E-01
<i>Ddit3</i>	1.06	7.38E-03	-0.07	1.00E+00
<i>Ctsz</i>	1.07	7.08E-04	0.12	8.45E-01
<i>Myo5a</i>	1.08	2.71E-03	-0.02	1.00E+00
<i>Enpep</i>	1.08	9.29E-03	-0.14	1.00E+00
<i>Fhl1</i>	1.09	4.21E-03	0.43	4.23E-01
<i>Abcc4</i>	1.09	3.90E-06	0.24	5.18E-01
<i>Mapk8ip1</i>	1.10	2.77E-02	-0.43	8.22E-01
<i>Ifit1</i>	1.10	2.71E-02	0.47	4.19E-01
<i>Rap1gap</i>	1.12	2.87E-02	0.17	8.82E-01
<i>Impdh1</i>	1.13	1.06E-04	-0.30	9.55E-01
<i>Mthfd2</i>	1.13	7.20E-03	0.52	3.82E-01
<i>Adgre1</i>	1.13	7.54E-05	0.44	2.32E-01
<i>C3ar1</i>	1.14	1.46E-02	0.23	7.27E-01
<i>Chn1</i>	1.15	1.74E-02	-1.14	1.64E-01
<i>Dhx32</i>	1.16	1.50E-03	-0.96	3.68E-02
<i>Gm49339</i>	1.17	2.36E-02	0.66	9.33E-02
<i>Sbk1</i>	1.17	1.20E-03	0.25	8.04E-01
<i>Osgin1</i>	1.19	3.03E-02	-0.39	1.00E+00
<i>Cyb5r1</i>	1.20	6.07E-06	-0.10	1.00E+00
<i>Htatip2</i>	1.20	1.50E-02	-0.66	5.75E-01
<i>Adap1</i>	1.22	3.47E-03	0.10	9.95E-01
<i>Dixdc1</i>	1.23	1.35E-03	-0.44	7.97E-01
<i>Tlr8</i>	1.24	2.26E-02	0.50	2.50E-01
<i>Adam8</i>	1.25	1.12E-03	0.53	1.44E-01
<i>Rassf3</i>	1.25	3.18E-04	0.00	1.00E+00
<i>Adamts15</i>	1.26	2.05E-06	0.24	6.35E-01
<i>Hk3</i>	1.27	1.11E-02	0.55	2.50E-01
<i>Nrcam</i>	1.27	3.76E-02	1.11	9.24E-02
<i>Rnf144b</i>	1.27	2.67E-04	0.06	9.74E-01
<i>Ccdc3</i>	1.27	2.07E-04	-1.36	9.95E-02

<i>Cryab</i>	1.32	8.11E-04	-0.94	4.94E-01
<i>Rdh11</i>	1.35	1.79E-03	-0.09	1.00E+00
<i>Gnao1</i>	1.36	2.04E-03	-0.79	8.36E-01
<i>Lipa</i>	1.36	2.79E-06	-0.11	1.00E+00
<i>Sfrp1</i>	1.37	2.13E-02	0.32	8.45E-01
<i>Fam69b</i>	1.39	7.07E-03	-0.65	6.55E-01
<i>Ftl1</i>	1.43	1.01E-06	0.17	7.24E-01
<i>Ms4a14</i>	1.44	3.78E-02	0.49	5.76E-01
<i>Stac</i>	1.44	1.38E-02	0.44	7.53E-01
<i>Ank</i>	1.47	6.07E-06	-0.42	7.38E-01
<i>Ms4a7</i>	1.50	5.04E-04	0.79	5.66E-02
<i>Ugp2</i>	1.50	1.29E-07	-0.34	1.00E+00
<i>Gclm</i>	1.51	6.83E-09	-0.05	1.00E+00
<i>Fam57b</i>	1.51	6.54E-04	-1.43	6.83E-02
<i>Kcnk3</i>	1.52	7.03E-05	-1.05	6.08E-02
<i>Chchd10</i>	1.52	1.06E-04	-0.42	9.96E-01
<i>Rtn4r</i>	1.52	1.23E-02	1.13	9.61E-02
<i>2010003K11Rik</i>	1.53	2.91E-02	-1.72	1.37E-01
<i>Dhrs9</i>	1.53	2.61E-03	0.88	9.99E-02
<i>Ftl1-ps1</i>	1.53	2.06E-02	0.20	8.62E-01
<i>Aqp11</i>	1.53	4.64E-02	-0.71	6.88E-01
<i>Hspb8</i>	1.54	8.48E-07	-0.33	1.00E+00
<i>Rsad2</i>	1.56	1.40E-06	0.26	7.89E-01
<i>Rnf128</i>	1.58	1.76E-03	0.35	7.93E-01
<i>Palm2</i>	1.60	1.05E-02	-0.42	1.00E+00
<i>Fbxo27</i>	1.61	3.83E-03	-0.72	6.16E-01
<i>Dscam</i>	1.62	5.67E-03	0.86	3.88E-01
<i>Atf5</i>	1.62	3.97E-08	-0.64	5.17E-01
<i>Mid1ip1</i>	1.62	7.77E-06	-0.44	8.05E-01
<i>Ephx1</i>	1.65	7.63E-11	0.24	5.22E-01
<i>Angptl8</i>	1.66	3.98E-04	-0.64	7.32E-01
<i>Reep6</i>	1.68	6.75E-11	-0.53	7.68E-01
<i>Igsf21</i>	1.69	4.41E-02	-0.60	1.00E+00
<i>Lonrf3</i>	1.69	2.91E-02	0.14	9.76E-01
<i>Prrt4</i>	1.69	3.40E-02	-0.52	9.46E-01
<i>Pcdha11</i>	1.70	2.62E-02	0.30	7.98E-01
<i>Lgals3</i>	1.71	5.11E-08	0.67	3.59E-02
<i>Slc7a11</i>	1.72	2.27E-09	0.55	6.67E-01
<i>9530053A07Rik</i>	1.72	4.41E-02	-0.13	1.00E+00
<i>Spp1</i>	1.84	4.96E-03	-1.54	9.22E-01
<i>Rwdd2a</i>	1.85	6.01E-03	-0.26	1.00E+00
<i>Hmox1</i>	1.85	3.77E-12	0.64	9.02E-02
<i>Apoc2</i>	1.85	4.47E-02	-0.31	1.00E+00
<i>Tmem82</i>	1.94	1.90E-02	0.53	7.85E-01
<i>Maff</i>	1.95	2.53E-06	0.14	9.34E-01
<i>Il1rn</i>	1.99	3.05E-02	1.31	5.24E-02
<i>Trib3</i>	2.03	2.75E-06	-0.41	9.31E-01
<i>Krt15</i>	2.07	3.23E-02	-0.68	1.00E+00
<i>Gprn2</i>	2.08	1.46E-02	-0.20	1.00E+00
<i>Preli3a</i>	2.09	2.12E-04	0.56	8.60E-01
<i>Peg10</i>	2.11	1.75E-11	0.28	8.45E-01
<i>Srxn1</i>	2.12	5.18E-12	0.31	4.50E-01
<i>Camk1g</i>	2.14	4.72E-02	-0.10	1.00E+00
<i>Plin2</i>	2.15	3.42E-11	-0.73	8.32E-01
<i>Sorcs2</i>	2.17	1.71E-08	0.21	1.00E+00
<i>Ppp1r3b</i>	2.25	3.58E-07	-0.28	1.00E+00
<i>Hpd1</i>	2.25	6.96E-03	-0.49	1.00E+00
<i>Atf3</i>	2.33	5.11E-08	0.42	5.33E-01
<i>Ccn5</i>	2.36	1.98E-06	0.01	1.00E+00
<i>Tchh</i>	2.36	1.67E-02	0.75	3.56E-01
<i>Kcng4</i>	2.39	5.96E-04	0.10	1.00E+00
<i>F7</i>	2.43	1.12E-02	1.40	8.97E-02
<i>Ccdc92</i>	2.49	1.82E-07	0.93	6.36E-02
<i>Acot11</i>	2.49	1.28E-13	0.46	4.62E-01
<i>Cbr3</i>	2.50	1.37E-10	0.53	3.15E-01
<i>Slc2a5</i>	2.53	1.43E-03	-2.11	2.43E-01
<i>Dusp9</i>	2.53	5.82E-04	-0.89	6.63E-01

<i>Aspg</i>	2.56	2.09E-10	-0.44	1.00E+00
<i>Elfn1</i>	2.56	2.61E-03	0.80	4.39E-01
<i>Tsku</i>	2.86	3.40E-21	0.70	3.95E-02
<i>Maoa</i>	2.86	1.16E-21	0.87	7.88E-03
<i>Trem2</i>	2.96	6.86E-07	0.92	1.73E-01
<i>Pla2g2e</i>	3.05	7.77E-06	-1.89	5.57E-01
<i>Lctl</i>	3.12	1.28E-21	-0.83	7.34E-01
<i>Atp1a3</i>	3.16	6.33E-13	0.20	1.00E+00
<i>Mogat2</i>	3.46	3.70E-12	-0.19	1.00E+00
<i>Phospho1</i>	3.53	1.20E-18	0.29	9.95E-01
<i>Tekt1</i>	3.78	2.39E-04	0.40	9.88E-01
<i>Dmkn</i>	3.95	1.99E-02	0.49	8.62E-01
<i>Heph11</i>	3.98	1.82E-07	-0.87	1.00E+00
<i>Atp6v0d2</i>	4.39	1.33E-09	1.39	5.84E-02
<i>Mmp12</i>	4.45	1.48E-15	0.89	6.02E-01

(B) DEGs (136 genes) that were changed by *Nampt* knockout in both young and old mice.

Gene symbol	Young (Log ₂ FC)	Young (FDR)	Old (Log ₂ FC)	Old (FDR)
<i>Hcar1</i>	-2.72	2.10E-22	-3.74	1.18E-19
<i>Mup10</i>	-2.68	8.17E-16	-3.05	8.64E-07
<i>Wfdc21</i>	-2.58	2.91E-10	-3.30	3.35E-05
<i>Pck1</i>	-2.57	9.35E-16	-2.98	5.80E-12
<i>Rbp4</i>	-2.49	3.08E-13	-4.41	2.99E-35
<i>Cfd</i>	-2.45	9.52E-29	-5.19	7.95E-20
<i>Cyp2f2</i>	-2.45	3.24E-06	-2.67	1.76E-09
<i>Nnat</i>	-2.43	1.33E-17	-3.43	8.83E-09
<i>Rgs7</i>	-2.41	8.11E-08	-2.46	1.25E-03
<i>Acsm5</i>	-2.30	1.79E-08	-4.10	1.86E-10
<i>Slc7a10</i>	-2.18	2.44E-17	-3.41	4.28E-13
<i>Nnmt</i>	-2.16	6.14E-22	-2.91	1.22E-07
<i>Ffar2</i>	-2.15	2.03E-10	-2.56	9.45E-07
<i>Mettl7a2</i>	-2.13	7.36E-03	-2.41	4.38E-03
<i>Retn</i>	-2.13	2.84E-19	-4.15	4.50E-27
<i>Adcy5</i>	-2.04	5.26E-13	-2.20	2.24E-06
<i>Trpv1</i>	-2.03	3.05E-07	-2.92	8.88E-04
<i>Spon1</i>	-2.03	8.27E-12	-1.86	4.21E-08
<i>Syt14</i>	-2.00	1.73E-02	-2.07	2.15E-02
<i>Ces1f</i>	-1.98	4.02E-12	-3.25	4.50E-17
<i>Slc43a1</i>	-1.97	2.98E-10	-1.34	1.18E-02
<i>Vnn3</i>	-1.97	5.50E-10	-3.47	4.23E-10
<i>Slc1a3</i>	-1.88	4.45E-14	-2.28	2.42E-11
<i>Grin2b</i>	-1.87	5.30E-08	-2.54	5.69E-04
<i>Kcnk2</i>	-1.84	1.73E-05	-3.05	3.68E-11
<i>Chst1</i>	-1.83	5.81E-13	-1.66	5.81E-06
<i>Lrrn4</i>	-1.83	3.13E-03	-1.70	4.71E-02
<i>H1fx</i>	-1.82	5.45E-06	-1.46	2.84E-02
<i>Gpat3</i>	-1.78	5.50E-13	-2.31	1.18E-08
<i>Als2cr12</i>	-1.77	3.91E-04	-2.62	3.14E-06
<i>Cnr1</i>	-1.74	1.59E-07	-2.42	1.55E-06
<i>Gm5460</i>	-1.72	2.93E-03	-2.91	7.22E-05
<i>Prtn3</i>	-1.71	3.47E-03	-2.13	1.46E-03
<i>Glb1l2</i>	-1.65	1.12E-16	-3.12	5.34E-10
<i>Pxmp2</i>	-1.65	2.98E-05	-2.60	2.82E-06
<i>Apol6</i>	-1.64	1.20E-10	-3.33	1.76E-12
<i>Hcar2</i>	-1.63	1.34E-05	-1.70	9.76E-04
<i>St6galnac5</i>	-1.62	4.39E-09	-3.08	1.04E-06
<i>Opn3</i>	-1.62	1.28E-10	-1.60	1.76E-04
<i>Ppp1r1a</i>	-1.58	1.76E-11	-2.55	3.62E-06
<i>Igfals</i>	-1.56	3.95E-10	-1.65	2.31E-03
<i>Aldh1l1</i>	-1.56	6.80E-12	-2.73	3.67E-14
<i>Trim67</i>	-1.54	1.17E-05	-4.07	7.29E-08
<i>Bche</i>	-1.53	5.81E-13	-3.58	2.04E-17
<i>Lgals12</i>	-1.53	2.38E-09	-3.13	3.81E-15
<i>Cyp2e1</i>	-1.52	1.23E-05	-2.06	3.69E-04

<i>Zyg11a</i>	-1.52	3.35E-04	-2.07	6.65E-03
<i>Cbs</i>	-1.51	8.12E-04	-2.13	9.62E-05
<i>Adhfe1</i>	-1.50	9.70E-14	-2.70	4.25E-12
<i>Serpina3c</i>	-1.49	4.94E-15	-2.26	6.41E-06
<i>Gpt2</i>	-1.49	6.87E-09	-2.34	1.27E-07
<i>Acss3</i>	-1.49	2.74E-10	-2.17	9.97E-09
<i>Acvr1c</i>	-1.48	2.94E-10	-3.61	4.41E-15
<i>Sncg</i>	-1.48	2.39E-07	-3.70	1.21E-12
<i>Fam13a</i>	-1.47	1.08E-06	-2.42	1.71E-10
<i>Mettl7a1</i>	-1.45	9.72E-07	-1.94	1.55E-06
<i>Ifi2712a</i>	-1.45	3.18E-10	-2.17	2.94E-05
<i>Tshr</i>	-1.43	1.71E-08	-3.72	9.85E-19
<i>Eci3</i>	-1.43	1.87E-03	-2.99	4.93E-08
<i>Car3</i>	-1.42	2.64E-09	-3.16	9.33E-10
<i>Atp1a2</i>	-1.41	1.03E-08	-2.47	3.89E-05
<i>Tenm4</i>	-1.40	4.32E-11	-2.91	2.26E-11
<i>Ffar4</i>	-1.39	2.47E-06	-1.80	5.82E-04
<i>Bnip3</i>	-1.39	2.15E-10	-2.33	2.41E-07
<i>Ghr</i>	-1.38	8.07E-11	-2.53	1.39E-09
<i>D430019H16Rik</i>	-1.38	2.52E-03	-2.32	5.59E-05
<i>Pfkfb1</i>	-1.37	2.03E-10	-3.43	7.39E-20
<i>Apcdd1</i>	-1.37	7.24E-10	-2.41	1.49E-07
<i>Klf15</i>	-1.37	1.04E-10	-1.94	6.73E-06
<i>B3galt2</i>	-1.34	2.87E-09	-2.12	2.85E-11
<i>Cd59b</i>	-1.33	2.72E-02	-1.81	4.37E-02
<i>Amy1</i>	-1.31	3.22E-08	-3.67	2.21E-18
<i>Slc27a1</i>	-1.31	6.98E-06	-2.28	9.81E-08
<i>Art3</i>	-1.30	1.77E-08	-2.63	3.48E-10
<i>Lrp3</i>	-1.30	1.01E-07	-1.59	5.36E-04
<i>Cmb1</i>	-1.28	1.88E-05	-2.75	8.32E-08
<i>Cdkn2c</i>	-1.28	3.18E-09	-2.46	1.99E-14
<i>Gstz1</i>	-1.27	2.16E-08	-2.77	2.35E-12
<i>Adipoq</i>	-1.24	5.99E-07	-3.28	2.77E-13
<i>Adgrg2</i>	-1.23	1.68E-04	-1.22	4.80E-02
<i>Cldn22</i>	-1.22	4.88E-02	-2.54	2.58E-05
<i>Cmklr1</i>	-1.20	5.40E-09	-1.12	2.40E-02
<i>Fbxo21</i>	-1.19	1.16E-03	-1.54	4.87E-04
<i>Aldh6a1</i>	-1.19	8.21E-08	-2.66	1.29E-11
<i>Acsl1</i>	-1.19	1.61E-05	-2.46	6.27E-08
<i>Ivd</i>	-1.16	7.01E-07	-1.60	6.06E-06
<i>Fam83a</i>	-1.15	5.34E-03	-2.33	2.17E-04
<i>Kcns3</i>	-1.14	7.39E-04	-2.54	9.81E-08
<i>Dhtkd1</i>	-1.14	9.21E-04	-2.03	1.37E-05
<i>Trabd2b</i>	-1.14	2.39E-08	-2.48	1.86E-10
<i>Slc1a5</i>	-1.13	9.90E-07	-2.18	4.00E-09
<i>Pfkfb3</i>	-1.12	3.06E-07	-1.81	3.88E-05
<i>Klhl2</i>	-1.11	4.23E-10	-1.03	2.91E-02
<i>Cth</i>	-1.11	3.63E-02	-2.16	2.62E-02
<i>Hacl1</i>	-1.11	2.13E-04	-1.63	1.19E-04
<i>Ccdc80</i>	-1.10	4.29E-07	-2.14	8.27E-07
<i>G0s2</i>	-1.10	3.78E-07	-2.33	1.06E-05
<i>Plin1</i>	-1.09	9.77E-06	-3.17	4.04E-15
<i>Trf</i>	-1.09	1.08E-07	-1.74	1.26E-02
<i>Adrb3</i>	-1.09	5.79E-05	-3.21	4.03E-14
<i>Ctcf1</i>	-1.09	6.48E-03	-2.99	9.33E-10
<i>Atp2b4</i>	-1.08	1.66E-07	-1.48	2.16E-03
<i>Pla2g16</i>	-1.08	1.03E-05	-2.34	7.13E-09
<i>Prkar2b</i>	-1.08	1.92E-05	-2.38	1.99E-07
<i>Ankef1</i>	-1.07	8.45E-08	-3.68	3.54E-22
<i>Cd1d1</i>	-1.07	1.64E-03	-2.49	1.42E-10
<i>Arl4a</i>	-1.07	1.34E-07	-1.84	2.58E-08
<i>Zfp185</i>	-1.06	2.98E-04	-1.94	5.78E-07
<i>Steap4</i>	-1.06	5.78E-08	-1.69	2.15E-03
<i>Mcam</i>	-1.06	1.17E-06	-2.27	4.17E-08
<i>Tro</i>	-1.05	1.42E-03	-1.69	4.34E-03
<i>Mccc2</i>	-1.04	5.30E-08	-1.84	4.11E-07
<i>Fam110c</i>	-1.04	3.57E-03	-1.73	5.94E-03

<i>Selenbp1</i>	-1.03	1.61E-06	-1.40	3.51E-03
<i>Ces1d</i>	-1.03	4.15E-04	-3.42	4.04E-15
<i>Rasd1</i>	-1.02	1.68E-03	-1.75	1.04E-05
<i>Hp</i>	-1.02	2.87E-04	-1.84	4.60E-02
<i>Mc2r</i>	-1.01	6.11E-03	-3.65	6.14E-09
<i>Sfrp2</i>	1.01	4.56E-04	1.30	2.26E-05
<i>Phlda3</i>	1.06	8.03E-03	-1.32	2.05E-03
<i>Apod</i>	1.13	7.15E-03	1.08	8.94E-04
<i>Fbln1</i>	1.13	1.10E-03	1.33	1.14E-04
<i>Slc25a1</i>	1.21	2.27E-02	-1.33	2.49E-02
<i>Gadd45a</i>	1.26	2.44E-03	-1.20	1.75E-02
<i>Cpa3</i>	1.28	2.88E-03	1.30	5.11E-05
<i>Comt</i>	1.39	1.55E-03	-1.21	9.22E-04
<i>Tpsb2</i>	1.46	3.03E-05	1.28	1.12E-06
<i>Cma1</i>	1.52	1.15E-04	1.29	1.72E-05
<i>Penk</i>	1.54	1.91E-02	1.70	1.52E-11
<i>Mcpt4</i>	1.55	6.32E-07	1.62	1.07E-08
<i>Zfp949</i>	1.58	4.44E-10	1.15	1.48E-06
<i>Cela1</i>	1.69	2.16E-02	-2.25	1.95E-03
<i>Kcnj15</i>	1.95	1.37E-06	-1.77	1.48E-03
<i>Mrgprx2</i>	2.30	1.77E-02	1.92	5.70E-04
<i>Gpnmb</i>	3.40	5.10E-21	1.19	1.81E-02
<i>Gdf15</i>	5.37	3.12E-19	2.51	3.65E-05

(C) DEGs (655 genes) that were changed by *Nampt* knockout only in old mice but not in young mice.

Gene symbol	Young (Log ₂ FC)	Young (FDR)	Old (Log ₂ FC)	Old (FDR)
<i>Lrr1</i>	1.00	1.00E+00	-6.50	2.87E-03
<i>Gys2</i>	-0.72	6.92E-01	-4.93	3.10E-19
<i>Tmem45b</i>	0.78	2.12E-01	-4.65	2.22E-14
<i>Prr32</i>	1.04	9.08E-01	-4.44	7.29E-08
<i>Crtac1</i>	-0.60	1.00E+00	-3.87	6.08E-04
<i>Lep</i>	-0.64	1.76E-01	-3.84	1.41E-05
<i>Akr1cl</i>	-1.47	2.04E-01	-3.75	5.25E-08
<i>Otop1</i>	0.71	8.31E-01	-3.69	2.55E-04
<i>Timp4</i>	-0.55	7.44E-02	-3.60	3.43E-08
<i>Alb</i>	-0.80	9.30E-01	-3.51	1.66E-03
<i>Npr3</i>	0.13	1.00E+00	-3.50	3.28E-07
<i>Mogat1</i>	-0.80	2.75E-01	-3.46	1.12E-07
<i>Ranbp3l</i>	-1.63	1.70E-01	-3.37	8.84E-05
<i>Dio2</i>	-1.21	1.80E-01	-3.34	1.57E-02
<i>Adig</i>	-0.94	1.06E-04	-3.25	1.34E-18
<i>Sucnr1</i>	-0.79	2.04E-01	-3.23	2.12E-06
<i>Abcd2</i>	-0.99	2.12E-04	-3.07	1.38E-13
<i>Kng2</i>	0.35	1.00E+00	-3.06	5.43E-03
<i>Smoc1</i>	-0.90	7.62E-04	-3.01	1.18E-14
<i>Arxes2</i>	-0.81	1.07E-01	-2.97	2.63E-08
<i>Gnai1</i>	-0.62	5.38E-02	-2.96	7.53E-11
<i>Arxes1</i>	-0.85	4.52E-02	-2.96	1.72E-05
<i>Scd1</i>	0.21	1.00E+00	-2.93	1.98E-12
<i>Folh1</i>	-0.24	1.00E+00	-2.91	3.14E-04
<i>Plin4</i>	-0.84	4.13E-03	-2.90	1.19E-08
<i>Aoc3</i>	-0.24	9.46E-01	-2.90	6.21E-11
<i>Fabp4</i>	-0.52	2.60E-01	-2.90	1.63E-10
<i>Car5b</i>	-0.57	1.64E-01	-2.84	3.61E-18
<i>Sfrp5</i>	0.38	1.00E+00	-2.84	2.28E-03
<i>Mmd</i>	-0.73	2.13E-02	-2.79	3.43E-08
<i>Lipe</i>	-0.69	3.80E-02	-2.73	3.79E-13
<i>Klb</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-2.72	1.38E-13
<i>Pnpla3</i>	0.07	1.00E+00	-2.72	1.70E-12
<i>Gsta3</i>	0.73	5.43E-01	-2.70	4.52E-11
<i>Cidec</i>	-0.66	1.04E-01	-2.69	4.02E-07
<i>Thrsp</i>	0.36	1.00E+00	-2.69	8.00E-13
<i>Scd3</i>	0.51	1.00E+00	-2.68	1.30E-12
<i>Eepd1</i>	-0.69	6.13E-03	-2.68	5.24E-07

<i>Rims4</i>	0.21	1.00E+00	-2.67	2.31E-04
<i>Fasn</i>	0.35	1.00E+00	-2.67	4.44E-07
<i>Rgcc</i>	-0.88	4.75E-04	-2.65	3.48E-10
<i>Dbi</i>	-0.47	3.21E-01	-2.65	2.26E-11
<i>A530016L24Rik</i>	0.10	1.00E+00	-2.62	2.89E-12
<i>Mgll</i>	-0.43	2.97E-01	-2.61	5.86E-08
<i>Paqr9</i>	-0.41	5.78E-01	-2.60	4.03E-04
<i>Pnpla2</i>	-0.29	8.42E-01	-2.59	1.58E-09
<i>Bmp3</i>	-0.67	1.51E-01	-2.58	1.24E-05
<i>Topaz1</i>	-1.43	2.48E-01	-2.55	1.97E-03
<i>4430402I18Rik</i>	-0.55	8.39E-01	-2.51	3.83E-06
<i>Mgst3</i>	-0.81	7.36E-03	-2.51	9.97E-09
<i>Cd59a</i>	-0.37	5.31E-01	-2.49	7.32E-08
<i>Syt12</i>	-0.26	1.00E+00	-2.49	3.09E-03
<i>Mlxipl</i>	0.64	5.23E-01	-2.48	1.19E-08
<i>Cdo1</i>	-0.60	3.13E-02	-2.47	6.72E-11
<i>Rbm46</i>	0.57	1.00E+00	-2.46	8.78E-03
<i>Cdsn</i>	0.61	8.42E-01	-2.45	2.41E-09
<i>Slc22a2</i>	0.85	1.00E+00	-2.45	4.29E-02
<i>Golga7b</i>	-0.72	1.00E+00	-2.44	3.49E-02
<i>Sorbs1</i>	-0.94	3.14E-04	-2.44	6.21E-11
<i>Pparg</i>	-0.36	5.32E-01	-2.44	7.97E-13
<i>Acsm3</i>	-0.65	2.76E-01	-2.44	3.71E-03
<i>Tspan12</i>	-0.54	3.78E-02	-2.42	1.94E-10
<i>Aqp7</i>	-0.50	3.87E-01	-2.41	1.22E-07
<i>Agt</i>	-0.27	1.00E+00	-2.38	1.37E-04
<i>Adtrp</i>	-0.82	3.78E-01	-2.38	9.59E-03
<i>Mest</i>	-0.10	1.00E+00	-2.38	2.82E-02
<i>Pcx</i>	-0.34	8.05E-01	-2.38	4.64E-08
<i>Tmem179</i>	-0.35	7.43E-01	-2.37	3.66E-11
<i>Trarg1</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	-2.33	2.07E-07
<i>Scd4</i>	0.19	1.00E+00	-2.32	1.70E-07
<i>Elovl6</i>	1.02	4.01E-01	-2.32	6.39E-03
<i>Gldc</i>	-1.00	1.48E-01	-2.31	1.78E-04
<i>Cidea</i>	0.96	2.14E-01	-2.31	4.19E-02
<i>Chpt1</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	-2.31	5.30E-09
<i>Cav1</i>	-0.50	1.08E-01	-2.30	1.04E-05
<i>Sdsl</i>	0.40	1.00E+00	-2.30	2.25E-03
<i>Cd36</i>	-0.33	6.70E-01	-2.29	2.51E-06
<i>Fcor</i>	-0.28	1.00E+00	-2.28	1.30E-04
<i>Orm1</i>	-0.19	1.00E+00	-2.28	5.15E-06
<i>Fah</i>	-0.74	1.88E-03	-2.28	4.44E-07
<i>4931406C07Rik</i>	-0.48	1.34E-01	-2.27	1.63E-04
<i>Dhdh</i>	-0.26	7.76E-01	-2.26	1.36E-09
<i>Tmem182</i>	-0.19	1.00E+00	-2.26	6.85E-03
<i>Atp1a4</i>	-0.84	2.97E-01	-2.26	3.40E-02
<i>Nat8l</i>	0.38	1.00E+00	-2.24	1.02E-06
<i>Me1</i>	0.21	1.00E+00	-2.24	1.97E-05
<i>Gpt</i>	0.17	1.00E+00	-2.22	1.46E-08
<i>Lpl</i>	-0.42	4.32E-01	-2.22	8.43E-06
<i>Trhde</i>	-0.73	2.81E-01	-2.22	7.41E-07
<i>Fam217a</i>	-0.93	8.02E-01	-2.22	2.91E-02
<i>Dgat2</i>	0.14	1.00E+00	-2.21	4.69E-06
<i>Fads3</i>	0.34	1.00E+00	-2.21	1.24E-05
<i>Sycp3</i>	0.04	1.00E+00	-2.21	6.24E-04
<i>Sik2</i>	-0.58	4.85E-02	-2.19	1.33E-09
<i>Clstn3</i>	-0.83	3.53E-03	-2.19	3.98E-03
<i>Palmd</i>	-0.17	1.00E+00	-2.19	6.19E-06
<i>Fam213a</i>	-0.33	5.98E-01	-2.17	1.01E-09
<i>Acaca</i>	0.35	1.00E+00	-2.17	1.95E-04
<i>Ptch2</i>	-0.67	6.94E-01	-2.17	1.61E-04
<i>Slc5a3</i>	-0.23	9.03E-01	-2.17	3.96E-07
<i>Klhdc7a</i>	-0.29	7.69E-01	-2.15	3.59E-08
<i>Slc25a10</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-2.15	7.81E-08
<i>Gabbr2</i>	-0.23	1.00E+00	-2.15	3.51E-02
<i>Ephx2</i>	-0.06	1.00E+00	-2.15	5.53E-04
<i>Slc2a4</i>	0.30	1.00E+00	-2.13	5.06E-05

<i>Grb14</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-2.13	1.95E-03
<i>Dclk3</i>	-0.68	1.00E+00	-2.12	7.99E-03
<i>Gpd1</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-2.11	2.19E-05
<i>Negr1</i>	-0.83	4.94E-03	-2.11	4.02E-07
<i>Dmrt2</i>	0.29	1.00E+00	-2.11	3.50E-06
<i>Nol3</i>	-0.17	1.00E+00	-2.10	3.08E-04
<i>Fzd4</i>	-0.26	5.39E-01	-2.09	4.27E-05
<i>Lpgat1</i>	-0.59	3.63E-02	-2.09	7.92E-05
<i>Gsta4</i>	-0.41	1.00E+00	-2.08	7.19E-04
<i>Wdr93</i>	-0.42	9.29E-01	-2.08	2.11E-04
<i>Pm20d1</i>	-0.96	2.94E-01	-2.07	9.60E-03
<i>Ppp1r3d</i>	0.20	1.00E+00	-2.06	5.64E-04
<i>Slc36a2</i>	-0.59	8.74E-02	-2.06	5.85E-06
<i>Rbpms2</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-2.06	1.20E-06
<i>Irs3</i>	-0.38	5.64E-01	-2.05	1.48E-05
<i>Ehd2</i>	-0.68	4.78E-03	-2.05	9.16E-05
<i>Slc6a13</i>	0.16	1.00E+00	-2.05	9.39E-03
<i>Hacd2</i>	-0.56	7.83E-02	-2.05	2.22E-07
<i>Aldh1a7</i>	0.03	1.00E+00	-2.03	9.36E-06
<i>Ptprd</i>	-0.98	9.29E-06	-2.02	1.41E-08
<i>Slc24a3</i>	0.48	1.00E+00	-2.02	8.08E-07
<i>Clybl</i>	-0.62	4.78E-02	-2.02	2.51E-06
<i>Cyp4v3</i>	-0.22	8.17E-01	-2.02	2.10E-04
<i>Pppr4</i>	0.05	1.00E+00	-1.99	4.50E-02
<i>Mrps6</i>	-0.48	1.82E-01	-1.99	6.19E-06
<i>Acadm</i>	-0.36	3.58E-01	-1.98	1.52E-05
<i>Pde3b</i>	-0.99	2.46E-05	-1.98	3.59E-10
<i>Mcrip2</i>	0.10	1.00E+00	-1.98	1.77E-03
<i>Cebpa</i>	-0.46	2.46E-01	-1.98	3.59E-08
<i>Acox1</i>	-0.58	7.52E-02	-1.98	4.80E-06
<i>Hibch</i>	-0.65	2.83E-02	-1.98	8.49E-08
<i>Tmem120a</i>	-0.86	2.73E-03	-1.97	9.25E-06
<i>Adora1</i>	-0.39	5.17E-01	-1.97	6.21E-04
<i>Fgf13</i>	-0.47	2.18E-01	-1.96	9.50E-05
<i>Cavin2</i>	-0.62	3.60E-02	-1.96	1.03E-05
<i>Aldh1a1</i>	-0.38	2.53E-01	-1.95	3.95E-03
<i>Aifm2</i>	0.04	1.00E+00	-1.95	5.43E-06
<i>H2-Q10</i>	-0.39	5.31E-01	-1.94	1.38E-03
<i>Kcng2</i>	-0.78	1.00E+00	-1.93	1.56E-02
<i>Gm525</i>	-0.19	1.00E+00	-1.92	2.83E-02
<i>Ugt1a6b</i>	0.36	1.00E+00	-1.91	7.55E-04
<i>Mrap</i>	0.34	1.00E+00	-1.91	6.19E-06
<i>Abat</i>	-0.14	1.00E+00	-1.90	2.91E-02
<i>Tcf15</i>	-0.03	1.00E+00	-1.90	1.52E-02
<i>Hebp1</i>	-0.67	1.18E-02	-1.89	3.81E-06
<i>Cat</i>	-0.46	4.21E-01	-1.89	3.12E-06
<i>Tmem120b</i>	0.23	1.00E+00	-1.89	1.99E-09
<i>Gpihbp1</i>	-0.33	5.42E-01	-1.89	2.04E-06
<i>Hspa12a</i>	-0.83	3.35E-04	-1.88	4.11E-05
<i>Nrg4</i>	-0.42	3.81E-01	-1.88	5.87E-06
<i>Acad11</i>	-0.84	1.66E-02	-1.88	5.87E-06
<i>Tfr2</i>	-1.53	1.22E-01	-1.88	1.60E-02
<i>Hadh</i>	-0.44	1.67E-01	-1.87	1.55E-06
<i>Acss2</i>	-0.27	1.00E+00	-1.87	5.80E-04
<i>Cav2</i>	-0.28	5.17E-01	-1.86	2.08E-04
<i>Prkd1</i>	-0.32	8.90E-01	-1.86	2.46E-04
<i>Tln2</i>	-0.50	6.29E-02	-1.84	1.41E-03
<i>Fitm2</i>	-0.32	6.37E-01	-1.84	5.89E-06
<i>Abhd15</i>	-0.83	1.79E-03	-1.83	7.04E-05
<i>Katnal2</i>	-0.77	4.33E-01	-1.83	1.63E-02
<i>Lyplal1</i>	-0.12	1.00E+00	-1.83	9.20E-04
<i>Ppp2r1b</i>	-0.39	2.36E-01	-1.83	4.44E-07
<i>Sgcd</i>	-0.97	3.80E-05	-1.82	1.21E-03
<i>Hrct1</i>	0.09	1.00E+00	-1.82	3.78E-03
<i>Fgfr1</i>	-0.25	7.78E-01	-1.82	1.11E-05
<i>Pcbd1</i>	-0.18	1.00E+00	-1.82	4.34E-02
<i>Sort1</i>	-0.43	2.45E-01	-1.81	1.17E-05

<i>Agpat2</i>	0.71	4.27E-01	-1.80	3.32E-04
<i>Rasgrf2</i>	-0.43	1.61E-01	-1.80	2.69E-05
<i>Hoxc8</i>	-0.67	6.26E-03	-1.79	2.60E-05
<i>Hnmt</i>	-0.96	3.00E-02	-1.78	8.54E-04
<i>Phgdh</i>	0.04	1.00E+00	-1.78	1.99E-04
<i>Retsat</i>	-0.51	1.96E-01	-1.78	3.50E-05
<i>Eif4ebp1</i>	-0.07	1.00E+00	-1.77	7.02E-06
<i>Angptl4</i>	-0.55	6.85E-02	-1.77	5.26E-04
<i>Slc22a3</i>	-0.35	7.45E-01	-1.76	9.00E-05
<i>Acot4</i>	-0.69	8.04E-01	-1.76	7.31E-03
<i>Tkt</i>	0.44	1.00E+00	-1.74	8.30E-06
<i>Acaa1b</i>	0.38	1.00E+00	-1.74	1.58E-03
<i>Gstk1</i>	-0.56	1.80E-01	-1.73	5.78E-04
<i>Poln</i>	0.20	1.00E+00	-1.73	3.88E-02
<i>Fam184a</i>	0.49	1.00E+00	-1.73	1.74E-02
<i>Echs1</i>	-0.68	1.46E-02	-1.73	5.78E-07
<i>1700056E22Rik</i>	-0.22	1.00E+00	-1.72	2.03E-02
<i>Cdc42ep1</i>	-0.42	1.67E-01	-1.72	6.59E-05
<i>Gcsh</i>	-0.21	8.28E-01	-1.72	1.70E-03
<i>Sfxn5</i>	-0.69	2.93E-03	-1.71	2.41E-04
<i>Gm10392</i>	-1.19	8.23E-02	-1.71	1.06E-02
<i>Gm14412</i>	-0.34	1.00E+00	-1.71	2.22E-02
<i>Tdrp</i>	-0.33	4.01E-01	-1.71	1.29E-05
<i>Lrrc39</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-1.71	5.11E-03
<i>ldh1</i>	-0.41	2.07E-01	-1.70	5.38E-05
<i>Cavin3</i>	0.34	1.00E+00	-1.69	1.07E-02
<i>Cldn15</i>	0.38	1.00E+00	-1.69	1.39E-03
<i>Ric3</i>	0.42	1.00E+00	-1.69	1.27E-02
<i>Pccb</i>	-0.56	6.59E-02	-1.69	4.03E-06
<i>Ly6h</i>	-0.89	2.40E-01	-1.68	2.91E-02
<i>Vegfb</i>	-0.59	1.46E-02	-1.68	2.41E-06
<i>Echdc3</i>	-0.94	4.13E-03	-1.67	3.51E-04
<i>Lrrc27</i>	-0.07	1.00E+00	-1.67	5.24E-03
<i>Acp5</i>	-0.98	1.08E-06	-1.66	3.50E-05
<i>Lgals1</i>	-0.14	1.00E+00	-1.66	3.22E-03
<i>Cluh</i>	-0.18	9.61E-01	-1.66	6.41E-06
<i>Mut</i>	-0.63	2.65E-03	-1.66	5.89E-06
<i>Adamts5</i>	0.15	1.00E+00	-1.66	1.14E-02
<i>Wscd2</i>	-0.24	1.00E+00	-1.65	7.19E-04
<i>Cpt2</i>	-0.50	7.83E-02	-1.65	4.33E-04
<i>Insig1</i>	-0.11	1.00E+00	-1.65	1.76E-04
<i>Ginm1</i>	-0.02	1.00E+00	-1.65	4.59E-06
<i>Scp2</i>	-0.50	8.08E-02	-1.64	8.89E-06
<i>Mgst1</i>	-0.58	4.50E-02	-1.64	1.19E-04
<i>Ptgfr</i>	-0.98	2.50E-02	-1.64	4.83E-03
<i>Nid2</i>	-0.70	5.82E-03	-1.64	1.08E-02
<i>Amotl2</i>	-0.26	7.90E-01	-1.64	8.47E-05
<i>Pon3</i>	-0.77	5.52E-05	-1.64	2.79E-06
<i>Ptp4a1</i>	-0.15	1.00E+00	-1.63	5.39E-06
<i>Fry</i>	-0.60	1.95E-02	-1.62	2.05E-05
<i>Zfp423</i>	-0.52	1.21E-02	-1.62	1.33E-03
<i>Gpam</i>	-0.56	3.96E-02	-1.62	2.75E-05
<i>Spaar</i>	-0.36	5.34E-01	-1.62	6.47E-04
<i>Prps1</i>	-1.00	2.00E-05	-1.61	4.31E-04
<i>Prss27</i>	-1.22	2.43E-01	-1.61	3.64E-02
<i>Ormdl3</i>	-0.13	1.00E+00	-1.60	3.89E-05
<i>G6pdx</i>	-0.01	1.00E+00	-1.60	6.18E-05
<i>Aox1</i>	-0.35	4.21E-01	-1.60	3.59E-04
<i>Sult1a1</i>	-0.89	2.10E-04	-1.60	1.61E-04
<i>Hsd17b4</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-1.59	6.72E-04
<i>1700020L24Rik</i>	-0.58	5.00E-01	-1.59	2.10E-02
<i>Hipk2</i>	-0.04	1.00E+00	-1.59	1.73E-04
<i>Itga7</i>	-0.21	8.78E-01	-1.59	3.39E-02
<i>Abhd5</i>	-0.45	1.47E-01	-1.59	6.04E-04
<i>Sc5d</i>	0.66	4.54E-01	-1.59	3.08E-06
<i>Srpx2</i>	-0.13	1.00E+00	-1.59	2.40E-02
<i>Cnm2</i>	0.15	1.00E+00	-1.59	2.89E-04

<i>Sh3pxd2a</i>	-0.68	3.49E-03	-1.59	1.61E-04
<i>Mmp28</i>	-0.37	4.80E-01	-1.58	2.60E-03
<i>Etfb</i>	-0.34	3.69E-01	-1.58	6.77E-05
<i>Ctdspl</i>	-0.67	1.04E-02	-1.58	1.70E-05
<i>Gm19426</i>	-0.70	3.32E-01	-1.57	1.75E-02
<i>Lzts1</i>	-0.50	6.09E-01	-1.57	5.64E-03
<i>Tmem205</i>	-0.17	1.00E+00	-1.57	2.74E-03
<i>Decr1</i>	-0.37	2.97E-01	-1.57	6.99E-04
<i>Acads</i>	-0.39	2.66E-01	-1.56	3.01E-04
<i>Pank3</i>	-0.89	2.10E-04	-1.56	1.36E-04
<i>Mccc1</i>	-0.89	1.61E-05	-1.56	8.98E-06
<i>Pm20d2</i>	-0.36	9.96E-01	-1.55	3.04E-02
<i>Gm266</i>	0.63	1.00E+00	-1.55	4.02E-02
<i>Mdh1</i>	-0.31	6.05E-01	-1.55	2.57E-04
<i>Slc25a23</i>	-0.54	2.68E-02	-1.55	4.59E-06
<i>Eci1</i>	-0.41	2.50E-01	-1.55	6.35E-05
<i>Cib2</i>	0.09	1.00E+00	-1.54	2.18E-02
<i>Prr16</i>	-0.80	7.36E-02	-1.54	1.62E-02
<i>Dgat1</i>	-0.28	7.76E-01	-1.54	1.06E-05
<i>Col4a2</i>	-0.19	9.09E-01	-1.54	1.60E-02
<i>Echdc1</i>	-0.21	9.60E-01	-1.54	1.16E-03
<i>Acat1</i>	-0.84	6.09E-05	-1.54	1.60E-04
<i>Pygl</i>	0.77	4.69E-01	-1.53	7.91E-05
<i>Plagl1</i>	-0.35	4.13E-01	-1.53	1.07E-02
<i>Idh3a</i>	0.22	1.00E+00	-1.52	8.68E-03
<i>Syap1</i>	-0.12	1.00E+00	-1.52	1.89E-04
<i>Pdzd2</i>	-0.81	6.30E-04	-1.52	1.78E-04
<i>Exd1</i>	-0.74	2.02E-01	-1.52	7.69E-03
<i>Acly</i>	0.98	5.77E-01	-1.52	2.72E-02
<i>Acat2</i>	-0.30	7.06E-01	-1.52	9.65E-05
<i>Tdrkh</i>	-0.33	9.23E-01	-1.52	2.34E-02
<i>Isoc2a</i>	-0.76	2.29E-03	-1.51	1.24E-05
<i>Aco1</i>	-0.79	2.04E-03	-1.51	3.09E-05
<i>Rbp7</i>	-0.75	2.60E-01	-1.50	4.03E-02
<i>Tns1</i>	0.03	1.00E+00	-1.50	4.67E-03
<i>Lpin1</i>	-0.18	1.00E+00	-1.49	8.77E-04
<i>Hibadh</i>	-0.49	6.85E-02	-1.49	4.15E-05
<i>Kcnb1</i>	0.92	9.29E-02	-1.49	2.23E-04
<i>Apmap</i>	-0.32	5.61E-01	-1.49	1.85E-04
<i>Al464131</i>	-0.43	1.85E-01	-1.48	3.73E-02
<i>Ppp2r5a</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	-1.47	1.30E-05
<i>Gbe1</i>	0.49	1.00E+00	-1.47	1.21E-05
<i>Serpina3n</i>	-0.76	9.20E-05	-1.47	9.64E-03
<i>Cyb5b</i>	0.04	1.00E+00	-1.47	5.80E-04
<i>Pdha1</i>	-0.17	1.00E+00	-1.46	7.92E-05
<i>Chchd6</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-1.46	9.59E-03
<i>Heph</i>	-0.31	3.64E-01	-1.46	1.61E-04
<i>Pde1a</i>	-0.63	1.26E-01	-1.46	1.39E-03
<i>Kyat3</i>	-0.62	3.22E-01	-1.46	9.61E-03
<i>Pkp2</i>	0.40	1.00E+00	-1.46	3.43E-04
<i>Adipor2</i>	-0.79	1.88E-03	-1.46	1.37E-04
<i>Bckdhb</i>	-0.48	7.24E-02	-1.46	7.72E-05
<i>Slc2a13</i>	-0.96	9.61E-04	-1.45	7.23E-04
<i>Fam217b</i>	-0.38	8.46E-01	-1.45	8.86E-03
<i>Gnb5</i>	0.12	1.00E+00	-1.45	2.80E-03
<i>Mecr</i>	-0.58	1.62E-02	-1.45	3.67E-04
<i>Ntrk2</i>	-0.89	3.45E-05	-1.45	4.83E-03
<i>Chp1</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	-1.45	7.56E-04
<i>Psat1</i>	0.42	1.00E+00	-1.45	1.79E-02
<i>Dusp10</i>	0.61	5.11E-01	-1.44	6.67E-03
<i>Mpc2</i>	0.38	1.00E+00	-1.43	2.91E-04
<i>Etfa</i>	-0.27	6.70E-01	-1.43	1.09E-03
<i>Ech1</i>	-0.43	1.42E-01	-1.43	4.35E-03
<i>Dram1</i>	-0.56	1.98E-02	-1.43	6.29E-04
<i>Ndufb3</i>	-0.51	2.50E-02	-1.43	4.29E-03
<i>Svip</i>	0.08	1.00E+00	-1.43	3.06E-02
<i>Alas1</i>	-0.49	1.63E-01	-1.43	3.40E-02

<i>Inca1</i>	-0.75	1.01E-01	-1.42	5.69E-03
<i>Ywhab</i>	-0.39	2.88E-01	-1.42	8.76E-04
<i>Gsn</i>	-0.79	7.60E-04	-1.42	2.03E-02
<i>BC067074</i>	-0.71	1.50E-02	-1.42	2.98E-03
<i>Map1lc3a</i>	-0.30	2.71E-01	-1.42	9.53E-03
<i>Ifi27</i>	-0.38	4.01E-01	-1.42	1.34E-04
<i>Ahcyl2</i>	0.02	1.00E+00	-1.41	8.47E-04
<i>Adh1</i>	-0.12	1.00E+00	-1.41	7.47E-03
<i>Btnl9</i>	-0.30	5.97E-01	-1.41	2.41E-04
<i>Rad18</i>	-0.60	5.05E-02	-1.40	4.10E-05
<i>Por</i>	-0.48	1.73E-01	-1.40	2.10E-04
<i>Rtn4r11</i>	-0.42	2.45E-01	-1.39	1.50E-02
<i>Dbt</i>	-0.50	2.14E-02	-1.39	1.86E-04
<i>Nos3</i>	-0.64	1.11E-02	-1.39	3.28E-03
<i>Crat</i>	-0.23	8.40E-01	-1.39	4.41E-03
<i>Pcca</i>	-0.67	5.29E-04	-1.39	5.70E-04
<i>Nudt12</i>	-0.31	6.62E-01	-1.39	1.96E-02
<i>Acadslb</i>	-0.76	4.29E-04	-1.39	2.14E-03
<i>Crls1</i>	-0.40	3.32E-01	-1.38	1.97E-03
<i>Sntb1</i>	-0.27	5.70E-01	-1.38	9.88E-06
<i>Matn2</i>	-0.34	5.99E-01	-1.38	4.41E-03
<i>Galm</i>	-0.19	1.00E+00	-1.38	1.26E-03
<i>Tlcd1</i>	-0.35	6.08E-01	-1.38	3.16E-04
<i>Ralgapa2</i>	-0.51	7.24E-02	-1.37	1.81E-05
<i>Aldh2</i>	-0.74	5.17E-03	-1.37	1.60E-04
<i>Ndufb9</i>	-0.04	1.00E+00	-1.37	1.78E-03
<i>Dlc1</i>	-0.30	5.68E-01	-1.37	2.27E-03
<i>Gamt</i>	-0.03	1.00E+00	-1.37	3.11E-02
<i>Lhfp12</i>	-0.17	1.00E+00	-1.37	1.14E-02
<i>Slc18b1</i>	-0.45	1.69E-01	-1.37	3.12E-03
<i>Aacs</i>	0.36	1.00E+00	-1.37	1.45E-03
<i>Ybx2</i>	0.26	1.00E+00	-1.37	1.08E-02
<i>Pygb</i>	-0.46	1.67E-01	-1.37	6.70E-04
<i>Col4a1</i>	-0.26	6.87E-01	-1.36	3.66E-02
<i>Prodh</i>	-0.54	8.41E-02	-1.36	1.22E-03
<i>Aspa</i>	-0.18	1.00E+00	-1.36	3.92E-02
<i>Dnajc15</i>	-0.28	5.67E-01	-1.36	4.33E-04
<i>Aldh5a1</i>	-0.09	1.00E+00	-1.36	1.96E-02
<i>Ywhag</i>	0.01	1.00E+00	-1.36	1.21E-03
<i>Fggy</i>	-0.39	4.74E-01	-1.36	7.80E-03
<i>Fign</i>	-0.36	7.39E-01	-1.35	2.62E-02
<i>Dolk</i>	-0.44	1.44E-01	-1.35	3.01E-03
<i>Nsdhl</i>	-0.38	6.72E-01	-1.35	4.33E-04
<i>Fabp5</i>	1.10	7.62E-02	-1.35	2.27E-02
<i>Cisd1</i>	0.38	1.00E+00	-1.35	9.60E-03
<i>Tmem135</i>	0.14	1.00E+00	-1.35	2.87E-03
<i>Cox8a</i>	-0.15	1.00E+00	-1.34	3.16E-04
<i>Bckdha</i>	-0.31	5.41E-01	-1.34	6.04E-04
<i>Bscl2</i>	-0.56	3.78E-02	-1.34	1.46E-03
<i>Nudt7</i>	-0.20	7.85E-01	-1.34	7.78E-04
<i>Fam126b</i>	-0.40	7.06E-02	-1.34	1.78E-03
<i>Fmo1</i>	-0.43	1.26E-01	-1.34	7.42E-04
<i>Irs1</i>	-0.63	1.31E-02	-1.33	7.19E-04
<i>Grina</i>	0.17	1.00E+00	-1.33	1.48E-02
<i>Cd320</i>	-0.35	8.05E-01	-1.33	4.80E-02
<i>Ptger3</i>	0.42	1.00E+00	-1.33	3.43E-02
<i>Gm11273</i>	0.13	1.00E+00	-1.33	3.94E-02
<i>Ndufv3</i>	-0.03	1.00E+00	-1.33	4.11E-04
<i>Gys1</i>	-0.17	9.52E-01	-1.33	1.17E-02
<i>L3hypdh</i>	-0.50	1.21E-01	-1.32	8.68E-03
<i>Pex16</i>	0.01	1.00E+00	-1.32	1.73E-04
<i>Pex11a</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	-1.32	4.48E-03
<i>Gcat</i>	-0.22	1.00E+00	-1.32	8.59E-03
<i>Med12l</i>	-0.20	1.00E+00	-1.32	1.77E-03
<i>Sod1</i>	-0.44	1.68E-01	-1.31	2.91E-04
<i>Emc9</i>	-0.27	7.12E-01	-1.31	2.69E-03
<i>Ndufb6</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-1.31	1.86E-02

<i>Cavin1</i>	-0.33	3.61E-01	-1.31	2.75E-02
<i>Asns</i>	-0.11	1.00E+00	-1.31	2.05E-03
<i>Oxct1</i>	-0.31	3.17E-01	-1.30	2.62E-02
<i>Gnpat</i>	-0.29	4.84E-01	-1.30	2.17E-03
<i>Acbd4</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-1.30	7.26E-04
<i>Csad</i>	-0.71	3.81E-03	-1.30	1.73E-04
<i>Prrg3</i>	-0.23	1.00E+00	-1.30	3.99E-02
<i>Tspo</i>	-0.20	9.36E-01	-1.30	1.34E-03
<i>Sowahc</i>	-0.43	2.65E-01	-1.30	2.42E-03
<i>mt-Nd4</i>	0.16	1.00E+00	-1.30	7.10E-04
<i>C9orf72</i>	-0.43	1.14E-01	-1.30	8.65E-03
<i>Atp9a</i>	0.03	1.00E+00	-1.29	4.76E-03
<i>Proca1</i>	-0.89	3.98E-03	-1.29	4.28E-03
<i>Ap3s1</i>	0.12	1.00E+00	-1.29	2.23E-03
<i>Atpaf2</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-1.29	5.59E-03
<i>Dhrs7</i>	0.08	1.00E+00	-1.29	2.05E-05
<i>Miga2</i>	-0.29	5.78E-01	-1.29	1.56E-03
<i>1110032A03Rik</i>	-0.35	5.94E-01	-1.29	1.87E-03
<i>Ak2</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	-1.28	3.80E-04
<i>Napepld</i>	0.16	1.00E+00	-1.28	1.31E-02
<i>Irak1bp1</i>	-0.70	2.40E-01	-1.28	4.11E-02
<i>Agmo</i>	-0.68	2.30E-02	-1.28	6.96E-03
<i>Slc39a8</i>	-0.67	2.71E-01	-1.28	3.68E-02
<i>Lmo4</i>	-0.10	1.00E+00	-1.28	8.00E-03
<i>Aplp2</i>	0.61	5.21E-01	-1.27	5.66E-03
<i>Ablim3</i>	-0.18	8.49E-01	-1.27	1.06E-03
<i>Acaa2</i>	-0.20	8.39E-01	-1.27	1.81E-02
<i>Pxmp4</i>	-0.63	5.17E-03	-1.27	5.20E-03
<i>Uqcr11</i>	-0.39	2.56E-01	-1.27	5.98E-03
<i>Bcat2</i>	-0.93	3.41E-04	-1.27	9.63E-04
<i>Ndufs5</i>	0.05	1.00E+00	-1.27	2.34E-03
<i>Aco2</i>	0.13	1.00E+00	-1.27	1.20E-02
<i>mt-Cytb</i>	0.01	1.00E+00	-1.27	7.10E-04
<i>Prkaca</i>	-0.19	9.49E-01	-1.27	7.38E-03
<i>Arhgap29</i>	-0.22	7.83E-01	-1.27	4.48E-03
<i>Nudt18</i>	0.20	1.00E+00	-1.27	1.06E-03
<i>Nrip1</i>	-0.58	1.74E-02	-1.26	8.32E-04
<i>1600014C10Rik</i>	-0.56	7.58E-02	-1.25	5.36E-04
<i>Dld</i>	-0.04	1.00E+00	-1.25	3.40E-03
<i>Prss36</i>	0.26	1.00E+00	-1.24	2.61E-02
<i>Raver2</i>	-0.59	8.11E-02	-1.24	6.37E-04
<i>Zdhhc2</i>	-0.18	1.00E+00	-1.24	2.83E-02
<i>Uqcr10</i>	0.18	1.00E+00	-1.24	9.60E-03
<i>Hsd12</i>	-0.04	1.00E+00	-1.24	9.53E-03
<i>Mmachc</i>	-0.15	1.00E+00	-1.23	8.47E-03
<i>Anxa6</i>	-0.21	7.56E-01	-1.23	1.79E-02
<i>Pmvk</i>	-0.15	1.00E+00	-1.23	7.50E-04
<i>Akap1</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-1.23	4.26E-03
<i>Col15a1</i>	-0.07	1.00E+00	-1.23	4.07E-02
<i>Hsd17b12</i>	-0.04	1.00E+00	-1.23	1.29E-02
<i>Pdhb</i>	0.37	1.00E+00	-1.23	1.50E-03
<i>Uqcrcq</i>	0.17	1.00E+00	-1.23	7.31E-03
<i>Acad12</i>	-0.51	2.97E-01	-1.23	4.76E-02
<i>Ldhb</i>	0.49	9.57E-01	-1.22	2.27E-02
<i>Cyb5a</i>	0.31	1.00E+00	-1.22	9.91E-03
<i>Atp5b</i>	-0.01	1.00E+00	-1.22	1.14E-02
<i>Mfsd8</i>	-0.47	1.42E-01	-1.22	7.31E-03
<i>Lrrc24</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-1.22	1.39E-03
<i>Maob</i>	-0.56	3.61E-02	-1.22	1.00E-02
<i>Cox6a1</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	-1.21	6.39E-03
<i>Fmr1</i>	-0.36	3.91E-01	-1.21	2.86E-02
<i>Uck1</i>	0.08	1.00E+00	-1.21	2.72E-04
<i>Hadhb</i>	0.41	1.00E+00	-1.21	1.56E-02
<i>Cs</i>	0.13	1.00E+00	-1.21	6.08E-03
<i>Ndufa4</i>	-0.07	1.00E+00	-1.20	2.05E-02
<i>Oplah</i>	0.01	1.00E+00	-1.20	9.90E-03
<i>D10Jhu81e</i>	-0.12	1.00E+00	-1.20	1.31E-03

<i>Prnp</i>	-0.36	4.17E-01	-1.20	3.70E-02
<i>Msra</i>	0.36	1.00E+00	-1.20	4.07E-02
<i>Coq7</i>	0.43	1.00E+00	-1.20	4.35E-02
<i>Pex19</i>	0.01	1.00E+00	-1.20	4.76E-03
<i>Cd151</i>	0.09	1.00E+00	-1.18	2.55E-02
<i>Coq9</i>	-0.17	9.55E-01	-1.18	2.88E-02
<i>Dlat</i>	0.64	6.84E-01	-1.18	1.60E-02
<i>Ndufb8</i>	0.02	1.00E+00	-1.18	8.59E-03
<i>Cd302</i>	-0.41	2.40E-01	-1.18	2.70E-02
<i>C130074G19Rik</i>	0.70	3.50E-01	-1.17	5.27E-03
<i>Ldah</i>	-0.31	2.45E-01	-1.17	1.39E-03
<i>Rab34</i>	-0.19	8.20E-01	-1.17	3.22E-03
<i>Cldn5</i>	-0.25	9.06E-01	-1.17	1.52E-02
<i>Fdft1</i>	0.18	1.00E+00	-1.17	1.10E-03
<i>Dhcr24</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-1.17	1.44E-02
<i>Hint2</i>	-0.20	1.00E+00	-1.17	1.91E-02
<i>Bmp6</i>	-0.19	1.00E+00	-1.17	3.73E-02
<i>Laptm4b</i>	0.04	1.00E+00	-1.16	1.28E-02
<i>Atl2</i>	-0.50	1.73E-02	-1.16	3.54E-02
<i>Pgd</i>	0.93	9.63E-02	-1.16	3.17E-03
<i>Acadl</i>	-0.59	3.72E-02	-1.16	3.36E-02
<i>mt-Nd4l</i>	0.32	1.00E+00	-1.15	3.94E-03
<i>Mpp1</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	-1.15	3.94E-02
<i>Uqcrb</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	-1.15	1.01E-02
<i>Tmem43</i>	-0.51	1.77E-01	-1.15	2.04E-02
<i>Atp5k</i>	-0.15	1.00E+00	-1.14	2.15E-02
<i>Iscu</i>	-0.11	1.00E+00	-1.14	1.56E-02
<i>Mpv17l2</i>	-0.06	1.00E+00	-1.14	2.65E-02
<i>Mdh2</i>	0.14	1.00E+00	-1.14	3.63E-02
<i>Phka2</i>	-0.69	1.30E-03	-1.14	8.88E-04
<i>Deptor</i>	0.48	9.28E-01	-1.13	3.39E-02
<i>Pth1r</i>	0.81	1.47E-01	-1.13	2.50E-02
<i>Chchd2</i>	0.04	1.00E+00	-1.13	4.08E-02
<i>Ano10</i>	-0.15	9.30E-01	-1.13	1.14E-02
<i>Slc25a16</i>	-0.49	1.10E-01	-1.13	9.70E-03
<i>Etfdh</i>	-0.01	1.00E+00	-1.13	1.20E-02
<i>Bcap31</i>	-0.10	1.00E+00	-1.13	3.32E-02
<i>Atp5g3</i>	-0.18	9.22E-01	-1.12	9.70E-03
<i>mt-Atp6</i>	0.39	1.00E+00	-1.12	1.10E-02
<i>Plcb1</i>	-0.50	5.44E-02	-1.12	8.53E-03
<i>Tcaf1</i>	-0.26	4.32E-01	-1.12	1.47E-02
<i>Cox6b1</i>	-0.08	1.00E+00	-1.12	2.26E-02
<i>Bicap</i>	-0.44	1.46E-01	-1.12	2.57E-03
<i>Cox7a2</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-1.12	1.00E-02
<i>Mvk</i>	-0.06	1.00E+00	-1.11	2.66E-02
<i>Apex2</i>	-0.44	1.09E-01	-1.11	3.90E-03
<i>Sdha</i>	-0.16	1.00E+00	-1.11	1.05E-02
<i>Atp5o</i>	0.11	1.00E+00	-1.10	2.76E-02
<i>Bola3</i>	0.11	1.00E+00	-1.10	1.26E-02
<i>Sqor</i>	-0.55	1.62E-02	-1.10	2.34E-02
<i>Bpnt1</i>	-0.30	3.97E-01	-1.10	1.92E-02
<i>Prdx5</i>	0.29	1.00E+00	-1.10	3.90E-02
<i>Gale</i>	-0.25	7.32E-01	-1.10	1.33E-02
<i>Gsto1</i>	0.19	1.00E+00	-1.10	4.02E-02
<i>Haus7</i>	-0.65	3.69E-02	-1.09	3.08E-02
<i>mt-Co2</i>	0.35	1.00E+00	-1.09	1.05E-02
<i>Dhrs4</i>	-0.16	1.00E+00	-1.09	2.93E-02
<i>Cped1</i>	-0.37	2.00E-01	-1.09	3.50E-02
<i>Sdhb</i>	0.16	1.00E+00	-1.09	1.23E-02
<i>S100a1</i>	-0.23	8.46E-01	-1.09	2.29E-03
<i>Trap1</i>	-0.32	3.83E-01	-1.09	6.31E-03
<i>Suclg1</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	-1.09	2.92E-02
<i>Hagh</i>	-0.15	1.00E+00	-1.09	7.82E-03
<i>Cycs</i>	0.48	9.72E-01	-1.08	2.91E-02
<i>Aldh4a1</i>	-0.78	9.36E-04	-1.07	2.61E-02
<i>Sod2</i>	0.15	1.00E+00	-1.07	3.92E-02
<i>mt-Nd5</i>	0.24	1.00E+00	-1.07	9.57E-03

<i>Cox5b</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-1.07	2.24E-02
<i>Mmab</i>	-0.18	9.71E-01	-1.06	1.45E-02
<i>Pim3</i>	-0.20	9.60E-01	-1.06	7.76E-03
<i>Mtus1</i>	0.15	1.00E+00	-1.06	1.72E-02
<i>Mfn2</i>	0.16	1.00E+00	-1.06	3.75E-02
<i>Mtch2</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	-1.06	1.71E-02
<i>Uqcrrs1</i>	-0.11	1.00E+00	-1.06	2.50E-02
<i>Hsd17b10</i>	-0.50	6.14E-02	-1.06	1.35E-02
<i>Glr5</i>	0.29	1.00E+00	-1.06	2.43E-02
<i>2410015M20Rik</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	-1.06	1.35E-02
<i>Emc2</i>	-0.16	1.00E+00	-1.06	1.97E-02
<i>Lrfr4</i>	-0.25	8.54E-01	-1.06	4.15E-02
<i>Sh3glb2</i>	-0.47	7.89E-02	-1.05	8.80E-03
<i>Tmem143</i>	-0.31	3.83E-01	-1.04	1.18E-02
<i>Abcb8</i>	-0.11	1.00E+00	-1.04	7.55E-03
<i>Epb41l2</i>	-0.15	1.00E+00	-1.04	3.55E-02
<i>Agfg2</i>	-0.31	4.35E-01	-1.04	1.93E-02
<i>Ndufa10</i>	-0.01	1.00E+00	-1.04	2.58E-02
<i>Ttc7b</i>	0.09	1.00E+00	-1.04	2.75E-02
<i>Mocs1</i>	-0.42	1.46E-01	-1.03	1.74E-02
<i>C1qtnf12</i>	-0.63	1.28E-02	-1.03	3.61E-02
<i>ldh3g</i>	-0.10	1.00E+00	-1.03	2.65E-02
<i>Sfxn1</i>	-0.90	3.40E-04	-1.03	2.46E-03
<i>Lama4</i>	0.46	9.63E-01	-1.03	3.83E-02
<i>Gpx4</i>	0.40	1.00E+00	-1.03	2.49E-02
<i>Taldo1</i>	0.55	8.02E-01	-1.02	2.52E-02
<i>Rnf144a</i>	-0.45	7.29E-02	-1.02	1.69E-02
<i>Mrpl12</i>	0.31	1.00E+00	-1.02	3.70E-02
<i>D5Erttd579e</i>	0.29	1.00E+00	-1.02	3.10E-02
<i>Sh3glb1</i>	-0.19	9.29E-01	-1.02	2.45E-02
<i>Alad</i>	-0.44	8.41E-02	-1.02	7.81E-03
<i>Cox4i1</i>	0.17	1.00E+00	-1.01	3.36E-02
<i>Pex13</i>	-0.24	5.78E-01	-1.01	2.08E-02
<i>Phb</i>	0.21	1.00E+00	-1.01	2.11E-02
<i>Fads1</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	-1.01	8.86E-03
<i>Abcd3</i>	0.14	1.00E+00	-1.01	3.54E-02
<i>Ndufa9</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-1.01	4.57E-02
<i>Rps6ka3</i>	-0.02	1.00E+00	-1.01	2.93E-02
<i>Ppa1</i>	-0.36	3.52E-01	-1.01	4.66E-02
<i>Prdx3</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	-1.01	3.11E-02
<i>Atp5l</i>	0.05	1.00E+00	-1.00	4.76E-02
<i>Ndufa12</i>	0.03	1.00E+00	-1.00	4.76E-02
<i>Tlr13</i>	0.51	1.00E+00	1.01	3.79E-02
<i>Oas2</i>	0.39	1.00E+00	1.02	1.98E-02
<i>Olfml2b</i>	0.55	6.72E-01	1.02	6.30E-04
<i>Tlr7</i>	0.35	1.00E+00	1.03	7.69E-03
<i>Tmprss2</i>	0.44	1.00E+00	1.03	1.24E-02
<i>Fgf7</i>	0.64	9.52E-01	1.04	4.71E-02
<i>Scn2b</i>	0.12	1.00E+00	1.07	3.03E-02
<i>Sema3d</i>	0.13	1.00E+00	1.07	1.21E-02
<i>Opcml</i>	0.60	7.19E-01	1.08	2.01E-03
<i>Npy1r</i>	0.45	1.00E+00	1.09	8.89E-03
<i>Ltf</i>	1.13	9.02E-01	1.09	4.64E-03
<i>Cybb</i>	0.46	7.72E-01	1.10	5.81E-03
<i>Csrp2</i>	0.28	1.00E+00	1.10	1.48E-04
<i>Lrrc17</i>	0.71	5.08E-01	1.11	2.01E-03
<i>Epha3</i>	0.27	1.00E+00	1.11	2.12E-02
<i>Gabre</i>	0.11	1.00E+00	1.11	1.63E-02
<i>Plek</i>	0.29	1.00E+00	1.12	3.54E-02
<i>Islr2</i>	0.32	1.00E+00	1.13	2.65E-02
<i>Scn3b</i>	0.55	1.00E+00	1.14	4.09E-02
<i>Hpse</i>	0.39	1.00E+00	1.15	2.91E-03
<i>Wasf3</i>	0.56	1.00E+00	1.16	4.83E-03
<i>Astn2</i>	1.10	6.92E-01	1.16	1.06E-02
<i>Cd38</i>	-0.05	1.00E+00	1.17	1.72E-02
<i>Hmcn2</i>	0.50	1.00E+00	1.18	1.06E-02
<i>Lgi2</i>	0.02	1.00E+00	1.18	7.57E-03

<i>Sned1</i>	0.83	3.45E-01	1.18	5.00E-06
<i>Nbl1</i>	0.78	7.87E-02	1.19	2.27E-04
<i>C7</i>	0.93	5.78E-01	1.20	2.95E-03
<i>Efcc1</i>	0.52	1.00E+00	1.20	1.51E-03
<i>Syk</i>	0.23	1.00E+00	1.21	1.30E-02
<i>Oasl1</i>	0.97	3.00E-01	1.21	2.58E-02
<i>Ryr3</i>	0.28	1.00E+00	1.22	3.96E-02
<i>Gabra3</i>	0.59	9.33E-01	1.23	2.58E-04
<i>Hdc</i>	1.11	2.01E-01	1.23	5.80E-03
<i>Inmt</i>	1.00	3.34E-01	1.23	3.98E-06
<i>Pla2g2d</i>	0.03	1.00E+00	1.23	7.17E-03
<i>Ndst3</i>	0.42	1.00E+00	1.24	3.65E-02
<i>Gpm6a</i>	0.10	1.00E+00	1.24	1.95E-02
<i>Ccl8</i>	0.49	1.00E+00	1.26	2.07E-04
<i>Zcchc18</i>	0.17	1.00E+00	1.26	4.80E-02
<i>Cd300ld3</i>	0.49	1.00E+00	1.26	3.28E-02
<i>Prox1</i>	-0.20	1.00E+00	1.26	2.34E-02
<i>Prdm6</i>	0.56	1.00E+00	1.31	2.63E-02
<i>Siglec1</i>	0.26	1.00E+00	1.31	4.68E-03
<i>Tex15</i>	0.75	1.00E+00	1.33	3.16E-02
<i>Gdf10</i>	0.60	7.70E-01	1.33	4.59E-06
<i>Plac8</i>	0.30	1.00E+00	1.33	2.25E-02
<i>Masp1</i>	0.58	1.00E+00	1.33	9.90E-03
<i>Nkd2</i>	0.73	5.09E-01	1.35	3.66E-02
<i>Fmn2</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	1.37	2.52E-02
<i>Mzb1</i>	0.03	1.00E+00	1.37	2.50E-03
<i>Siglech</i>	0.01	1.00E+00	1.37	3.44E-02
<i>Slc6a4</i>	0.49	1.00E+00	1.40	1.16E-02
<i>Cacna1b</i>	0.01	1.00E+00	1.41	2.58E-02
<i>Igfbp3</i>	0.58	5.08E-01	1.43	1.73E-04
<i>Sema3a</i>	-0.23	1.00E+00	1.45	3.44E-02
<i>Col25a1</i>	0.55	1.00E+00	1.48	2.91E-02
<i>Mcoln2</i>	0.06	1.00E+00	1.48	3.39E-02
<i>Aox3</i>	1.28	7.95E-02	1.53	1.17E-05
<i>Fbxl13</i>	0.52	1.00E+00	1.53	4.03E-02
<i>Tnfrsf18</i>	1.14	1.00E+00	1.54	1.69E-02
<i>Vit</i>	0.80	9.04E-01	1.56	1.21E-05
<i>Clec1b</i>	-0.70	6.84E-01	1.58	4.09E-02
<i>Mdga2</i>	-0.21	1.00E+00	1.59	1.98E-02
<i>Mrgprb1</i>	1.11	3.45E-01	1.63	1.09E-03
<i>Tmem132c</i>	0.47	1.00E+00	1.63	8.58E-06
<i>Tnfrsf6</i>	1.18	2.28E-01	1.66	4.21E-02
<i>Hcrtr2</i>	-0.40	1.00E+00	1.67	4.94E-02
<i>Tmem26</i>	0.37	1.00E+00	1.70	9.61E-03
<i>Sfrp4</i>	0.71	4.44E-01	1.72	8.69E-06
<i>Rgs17</i>	0.36	1.00E+00	1.74	2.51E-02
<i>Sntg1</i>	-0.74	8.31E-01	1.74	1.43E-03
<i>Ch25h</i>	-0.13	1.00E+00	1.78	4.12E-02
<i>Fcrl5</i>	-0.41	1.00E+00	1.81	3.61E-02
<i>Dkk2</i>	0.62	1.00E+00	1.82	8.68E-03
<i>AC132444.1</i>	-0.89	1.00E+00	1.86	3.95E-02
<i>Mcoln3</i>	-0.13	1.00E+00	1.86	3.98E-02
<i>Trim30b</i>	-0.10	1.00E+00	1.86	3.40E-02
<i>Anks1b</i>	0.04	1.00E+00	1.87	3.42E-03
<i>Dbx2</i>	-0.45	1.00E+00	1.91	1.10E-02
<i>Il10</i>	0.09	1.00E+00	1.92	1.27E-02
<i>Tdo2</i>	0.21	1.00E+00	1.96	2.76E-02
<i>Amph</i>	0.19	1.00E+00	1.96	2.25E-03
<i>Cd209b</i>	-0.22	1.00E+00	1.96	3.25E-03
<i>Cdh22</i>	0.35	1.00E+00	2.03	2.50E-02
<i>Cxcl13</i>	0.05	1.00E+00	2.05	1.08E-02
<i>Lipg</i>	0.26	1.00E+00	2.06	3.31E-02
<i>Fras1</i>	0.81	9.30E-01	2.10	2.40E-02
<i>Lsamp</i>	0.55	1.00E+00	2.18	4.33E-04
<i>5530401A14Rik</i>	-0.56	1.00E+00	2.18	2.52E-02
<i>Cyp11a1</i>	1.18	7.76E-01	2.26	5.59E-04
<i>Slc1a2</i>	0.24	1.00E+00	2.27	8.89E-03

<i>Cd5l</i>	0.22	1.00E+00	2.31	3.38E-02
<i>Npy2r</i>	-0.25	1.00E+00	2.46	3.84E-03
<i>Agbl1</i>	-0.06	1.00E+00	2.47	2.03E-02
<i>Slc6a1</i>	1.19	9.40E-01	2.48	4.67E-02
<i>Tpsg1</i>	0.68	1.00E+00	2.56	1.54E-04
<i>Il13ra2</i>	0.13	1.00E+00	2.66	1.58E-03
<i>Ache</i>	0.30	1.00E+00	2.71	2.45E-06
<i>Csrmp3</i>	0.00	1.00E+00	2.75	8.52E-03
<i>Snap91</i>	-0.57	1.00E+00	2.76	2.58E-02
<i>Col6a6</i>	0.80	3.20E-01	2.86	1.61E-04
<i>Crocc2</i>	2.31	1.18E-01	2.96	4.78E-09
<i>Ngp</i>	0.31	1.00E+00	3.39	5.36E-04
<i>Col6a5</i>	0.60	9.72E-01	3.44	1.59E-02
<i>Cdr1</i>	0.22	1.00E+00	3.52	3.50E-03

Differentially expressed genes (DEGs, false discovery rate [FDR]<0.05, |Log₂ fold change [FC]|>1) between flox/flox and ANKO mice were determined by using RNA-seq of WAT. DEGs with log₂-transformed FC and FDR values are shown.

Supplemental Table 3. A list of biological pathways significantly enriched with 655 DEGs that were changed in WAT by *Nampt* knockout in old mice but not in young mice.

GO ID	GO (Biological Process) Term	Fold Enrichment	FDR
GO:0006086	Acetyl-CoA biosynthetic process from pyruvate	25.0	2.21E-02
GO:0006102	Isocitrate metabolic process	20.8	3.52E-02
GO:0061732	Mitochondrial acetyl-CoA biosynthetic process from pyruvate	19.5	5.63E-03
GO:0009083	Branched-chain amino acid catabolic process	17.3	8.69E-03
GO:0042759	Long-chain fatty acid biosynthetic process	17.3	8.69E-03
GO:0019432	Triglyceride biosynthetic process	16.8	2.63E-04
GO:0033539	Fatty acid beta-oxidation using acyl-CoA dehydrogenase	16.4	7.11E-07
GO:0006123	Mitochondrial electron transport, cytochrome c to oxygen	13.0	2.67E-02
GO:0006734	NADH metabolic process	13.0	2.67E-02
GO:0050872	White fat cell differentiation	11.7	8.63E-03
GO:0019915	Lipid storage	11.6	1.91E-05
GO:0006107	Oxaloacetate metabolic process	11.2	4.45E-02
GO:0055088	Lipid homeostasis	9.9	8.61E-07
GO:0007031	Peroxisome organization	9.4	2.37E-02
GO:0016126	Sterol biosynthetic process	9.3	2.20E-03
GO:0006749	Glutathione metabolic process	8.9	8.08E-07
GO:0006633	Fatty acid biosynthetic process	8.4	4.83E-10
GO:0009409	Response to cold	7.0	3.10E-03
GO:0014823	Response to activity	6.4	2.52E-03
GO:0008217	Regulation of blood pressure	5.5	2.67E-03
GO:0051289	Protein homotetramerization	5.1	2.52E-03
GO:0008152	Metabolic process	4.9	1.59E-26
GO:0055114	Oxidation-reduction process	4.9	4.46E-39
GO:0045444	Fat cell differentiation	4.7	3.65E-03
GO:0006629	Lipid metabolic process	4.7	8.32E-24
GO:0008202	Steroid metabolic process	4.5	6.06E-03
GO:0007584	Response to nutrient	4.3	3.14E-02
GO:0045471	Response to ethanol	4.0	2.52E-03
GO:0006979	Response to oxidative stress	4.0	7.57E-04
GO:0016042	Lipid catabolic process	3.4	4.16E-02
GO:0005975	Carbohydrate metabolic process	3.3	4.95E-04
GO:0042493	Response to drug	2.7	7.01E-04
GO:0006810	Transport	1.6	2.01E-04

Significantly (FDR<0.05) enriched pathways of 655 DEGs that were changed in WAT by *Nampt* knockout only in old mice but not in young mice (Supplemental Table 2C) were identified using the DAVID Bioinformatics Resources (see the Materials and Methods section for details). Fold enrichment score and FDR values are shown.

Supplemental Figure 1

Supplemental Figure 1. NAD⁺ metabolites in white adipose tissue (WAT) obtained from old female ANKO and flox/flox mice.

The levels of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺) and key NAD⁺ metabolites in WAT obtained from old (≥ 18 -month-old) flox/flox and ANKO mice ($n=3-5$ per group). Nam; nicotinamide, NMN; nicotinamide mononucleotide, NR; nicotinamide riboside, Tryp; tryptophan; NA, nicotinic acid, NaMN; nicotinic acid mononucleotide, NaAD⁺; nicotinic acid adenine dinucleotide. Values are means $\pm$ SEM. Data were analyzed by Student's unpaired t test. * $P<0.05$; ** $P<0.01$; *** $P<0.001$.

Supplemental Figure 2

Supplemental Figure 2. Tissue weight of fat depots in old female ANKO mice.

Tissue weight of white adipose tissue (WAT) depots in old (≥ 18 -month-old) flox/flox and ANKO female mice ($n=5$ per group). sWAT, subcutaneous WAT; eWAT, epididymal WAT; mWAT, mesenteric WAT; pWAT, perirenal WAT; BAT, brown adipose tissue. Values are means $\pm$ SEM. Data were analyzed by Student's unpaired t test. * $P < 0.05$.

Supplemental Figure 3

Supplemental Figure 3. Adipocyte-specific *Nampt* deletion protected against age-induced obesity.

Young (≤ 4 -month-old), middle-aged (10 to 14-month-old), and old (≥ 18 -month-old) male adipocyte-specific *Nampt* knockout (ANKO) and flox/flox mice were subjected to metabolic phenotyping. Body weight (A), fat mass (B) and lean mass (C) were determined using EchoMRI (n=4-5 per group). Values are means $\pm$ SEM. Data were analyzed by Student's unpaired t test. *P<0.05.

Supplemental Figure 4

Supplemental Figure 4. Young ANKO mice were insulin-resistant and metabolically unhealthy.

Whole-body and tissue-specific glucose metabolism was evaluated in young (2 to 4-month-old) female mice. Blood glucose (A) and plasma insulin concentrations (B) during intraperitoneal glucose tolerance tests (n=3-7 per group). (C) Blood glucose concentration during insulin tolerance tests (n=6-8 per group). (D-H) Hyperinsulinemic euglycemic clamp procedure (HECP) was performed. (D) Glucose infusion rate (GIR) during the HECP and average of GIR during the clamp period (n=8-10 per group). (E) Glucose turnover in basal and insulin-stimulated conditions (n=4-5 per group). (F) Insulin-stimulated glucose uptake in skeletal muscle, heart, and WAT (n=4-5 per group). Hepatic glucose production (HGP) (G) and plasma free fatty acids (FFA) concentrations (H) during the HECP (n=4-5 per group). Plasma insulin (I) (n=4-5 per group) and adiponectin and adipisin (J) concentrations (n=3-6 per group). Values are means $\pm$ SEM. #ANOVA revealed a significant group x time interaction ($P < 0.05$). Data were analyzed by Student's unpaired t test. * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$.

Supplemental Figure 5

Supplemental Figure 5. Whole-body and hepatic insulin sensitivity in young and old control (flox/flox) female mice.

GIR (A) and insulin-stimulated percent suppression of basal HGP (B) were determined in control (flox/flox) female mice during the HECF (n=5-10 per group). Values are means $\pm$ SEM. Data were analyzed by Student's unpaired t test. *P<0.05.

Supplemental Figure 6

Supplemental Figure 6. Metabolic phenotype in old male ANKO mice.

Blood glucose concentration during insulin tolerance tests (A), plasma insulin (B) and adiponectin and adipisin (C) concentrations were determined in 16 to 25-month-old male ANKO and flox/flox mice (n=5-7 per group). Values are means $\pm$ SEM. #ANOVA revealed a significant group x time interaction (P<0.05). Data were analyzed by Student's unpaired t test. *P<0.05; **P<0.001.

Supplemental Figure 7

Supplemental Figure 7. Loss of NAMPT did not affect markers of adipose tissue fibrosis in old mice.

(A) WAT expression of collagen 3a1 (*Col3a1*), collagen 5a1 (*Col5a1*), and collagen 6a1 (*Col6a1*) were determined by using Real-time PCR analysis in old (≥ 18 -month-old) female flox/flox and ANKO mice (n=5 per group). (B) ANKO mice had similar levels of hydroxyproline, a key biomarker of fibrosis, to flox/flox mice (n=3 per group). Values are means $\pm$ SEM. Data were analyzed by Student's unpaired t test.

Supplemental Figure 8

Supplemental Figure 8. Rosiglitazone administration did not have a major impact on whole-body and cellular metabolism in old B6 female mice.

A PPAR γ agonist, rosiglitazone (RSG), was administered to 22-month-old female C57BL6/J mice (n=5-7 per group). Body weight (A), subcutaneous WAT (sWAT) and epididymal WAT (eWAT) weight (B), fasting glucose (C), insulin (D), insulin tolerance (E), and adiponectin and adipsin (F) in RSG-treated and -untreated B6 mice. (G) WAT gene expression of PPAR γ S273 and lipogenic targets. Values are means $\pm$ SEM. *P<0.01.